

FLEXURAL PERFORMANCE OF NANO-PARTICLE REINFORCED UV-CURABLE RESINS MANUFACTURED BY STEREOLITHOGRAPHY

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Keywords: Additive manufacturing, stereolithography, nanocomposites, mechanical testing

ABSTRACT

A portion of a more conclusive testing matrix applied to nano-particle reinforced UV-curable resins for their application to additive manufacturing by stereolithography is presented. A low cost desktop printer Anycubic Photon Mono X 4K SLA machine is used in the manufacturing efforts. Nano-composite samples of two types of SLA resins (tough and rigid) reinforced with 4 different types of different nanoparticles (Al_2O_3 , B_4C , SiO_2 , SiC) at two different filling ratio (1 wt. % and 5. wt.%) are targeted. The effect of nanoparticles has been searched on bottom layer/normal layer interfaces and on bulk response of normal printing layers. In overall a general assessment of 32 experimentation points in terms of their flexural strength, manufacturability and color. Fast and reliable printing of nanocomposite parts with Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 nanoparticles up to 5wt.% was achieved. Printing of UV-curable resins with SiC B_4C was dependent on the resin type and manufacturing of nanocomposites with 5 wt.% B_4C was not possible. Among all candidates the use of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles resulted in flexural strength increase in both type of resins and both type of specimen types while changing the part color to creamy white from transparent. Other particles contributed negatively to the strength of rigid resin due to potential agglomerations especially in the case of 1-5 wt.% SiC and 1% B_4C . In the case of tough resins, all of the suggested particle types provided strength to printed parts both on bottom layer/normal layer interface and inside normal layers. Overall it can be suggested that, both mechanical response and the color of tough line resins can be tuned with the addition of nano-sized particles.

1 INTRODUCTION

Usage of additive manufacturing (AM) technique is increasing parallel to industrial needs and rapidly advancing manufacturing technologies. One of the root concerns of such technologies is the development of adaptable materials that meet the more precise demands [1]. Among existing AM techniques, stereolithography deserves attention thanks to its inherent manufacturing speed and precision achieved by photocurable resin processing [2]. From material science perspective, the repetitive micro-structures achieved by the printer resolution and locally controlled resin curing allow for quick and repeatable data generation for material development. Hence, stereolithography process enables the implementation of conventional thermoset toughening methods especially by the integration of nano-sized particles even by desktop level printers [3].

With advancing demand and manufacturing efforts, the cost of such nano-particles is decreasing which enables their usage in novel manufacturing processes. Being one of those, stereolithography (SLA) technique offers a fast and reliable way for assessing the integrability of nano-particles into UV-curable resins [4]. When combined with high printing resolution, hierarchical polymeric composites with varying resin and inclusion with different micro-architectures are obtainable [5,6]. When combined with recent engineering approaches for polymeric nano-composites, the adaptation to SLA process may enable fast, reliable and cost-effective material solutions that are even applicable on low cost desktop printers.

Silica nanoparticles (SiO_2) are widely studied in various nano-composite applications due to their low cost, hydrophilic structure, good biocompatibility, large specific surface areas, pore volumes and

controlled particle sizes [8]. The adaptation of SiO₂ nanoparticles to SLA has been the initial focus of recently reported works [9-10]

Being equally abundant, aluminum oxide has different characteristics such as high hardness, strength, wear resistance, catalytic activity, hardness, thermal conductivity, good dielectric properties, chemical inertness, high melting temperature, friction and high optical band gap. [11].

Different from the metal oxide alternatives SiC and B₄C can be considered as relatively expensive nanoparticles with significantly improved stiffness and hardness characteristics. The usage of such nanoparticles in rather conventional resin types has been thoroughly reviewed and the targeted applications of these nanocomposites have been specified as sensors, catalyst supports, energy storage materials, structural reinforcement, and semiconductor materials. B₄C particles can also be classified as high hardness and stiffness material types that are more expensive than SiC. Although the price constraint limits their applications, their usage in low amounts as exemplified in this work, might be of interest. Implementation of such nanoparticles to additive manufacturing has been exemplified for binder jetting technology [12] and direct ink writing [13], however no existing reports on SLA manufacturing has been found.

In this study, a total of two resins from manufacturer will be used in nanocomposite preparation. Tough and rigid line serial products will be compared: ACT tough line, AC rigid line from Anycubic brand. First, specimens using rigid line and tough line resins will be prepared as references, followed by the preparation of the composites with different contents of nanoparticles. Silica (SiO₂), Alumina (Al₂O₃), Boron Carbide (B₄C), and Silicon Carbide (SiC) will be incorporated into the resins in 1 wt.% and 5 wt.%. Initial attention was given to manufacturability.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2 resin types were employed from Anycubic named as Tough (ACT) and Rigid(AC) product lines.

4 different types of nano-particles such as Al₂O₃, 10±5nm in size (purchased from Nanografi, TR with trade nameNG01NMO180256), SiO₂, 30-50 nm in size (purchased from Nanokar,TR), B₄C, 1-3 μm in size (purchased from Nanografi, TR), and SiC, 0.1 to 1 μm in size (purchased from Goodfellow, UK) were used as additives.

Nanoparticles were mixed at a designated ratio of 1 wt.% and 5 wt.% to each resin with a high-speed mixer at 60000 rpm for 20 minutes. Obtained nanoparticle/resin mixtures is then held for 10 minutes to remove formed air bubbles due to mixing.

Anycubic Photon Mono X 4K SLA machine was used for sample manufacturing. Single layer curing time was set to 4.5 seconds. Each sample consisted of 60 layers and has a layer height of 5 micrometers. Sample geometry was defined as designated in ASTM D790 standard.

Figure 1. SLA Printing Process

With applied manufacturing scheme 18 bending samples were manufactured in 14 minutes allowing for statistically enough tests for each case.

An important and rather undiscussed point in the literature and data sheets was the presence of bottom layers in the manufacturing. In order to provide a brief discussion, samples of neat resins with and without bottom layers were also printed.

After printing, samples were washed with ethanol for 10 minutes in a wash and cure machine, and then 20 minutes of post cure was applied at 405nm UV light. Bending tests were performed in Insight Laboratories (TR) with a Labomak (TR) 10 kN UTM machine with a constant crosshead speed of 5mm/min.

2.1 THREE POINT BENDING TEST

Three-point bending test was carried out by a testing machine. The size of all specimens was 56 mm × 12 mm × 3 mm (length × width × thickness). The span was 30 mm, and the loading speed was set to 2 mm/min. 18 specimens were tested for each composite to determine its ultimate bending strength.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 MANUFACTURABILITY AND COLOR

Significant manufacturing problems were encountered during trials of 5 wt.% B₄C for both resins, 5 wt.% SiC for tough line resin. This was contributed to adhesion problem of printed samples due to insignificant UV transmittance and insufficient curing. These test cases were excluded from testing scenarios.

Color is of importance when printing with SLA resins. Depending on the user demand black, gray, white and clear types of SLA resins are available in the market. The use of nanoparticles can provide different colors when used. Both types of neat resin types were colorless/clean and transparent. The addition of Al₂O₃ resulted in a less transparent creamy white color. Addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles on the other hand did not disturb the transparency of the samples. For SiC particles a dark brown color grade was obtained. Samples containing B₄C had a black color.

Figure 2. A) Tough-line nanocomposites B) Rigid-line nanocomposites C) A view from a manufacturing trial of 5%SiC + ACT resin D) A view from a manufacturing trial of 5 wt. %B₄C + AC resin

3.2 EFFECT OF NANOPARTICLES FOR PRINTING WITH THICK BOTTOM LAYERS

The bottom layer count is the number of first layers that you will expose UV light on for the set bottom exposure time. These layers ensure strong adhesion to the build plate and help in building a successful 3D model. The curing quality of the bottom layers is determined by the uv-exposure time whereas the thickness is determined with the bottom layer count. Depending on the type of SLA machine, manufacturers suggest a rather fixed bottom layer count for model manufacturing. In order to observe the effect of nano-particle adhesion to mechanical response of near bottom-layer region, three-point bending tests were performed to two types of specimens i) 8 layers for 8sec ii) 32 layers for 20sec (manufacturer suggestion).

Flexural strength of the samples with thicker bottom layer was measured to be higher than the samples with thinner bottom layer region. (Figure 5). In the case of tough line (ACT) resin, the best strength contribution was achieved via 5 wt. % Al_2O_3 addition (39 %). Addition of 1 and 5 wt. % SiO_2 resulted in similar strength improvements. It was also significant to observe that no strength reduction was seen with the addition of SiC with higher stiffness and potential dispersion problem.

Figure 3. %5 wt. SiO_2 + ACT samples with a) thin b) thick bottom layers

In the case of rigid resin (AC), only Al_2O_3 particles have positively contributed to the flexural strength (38 %) of samples with thick bottom layers. Addition of SiC resulted in significant strength reductions due to particle agglomerations. Cross-sectional micrographs taken from the fracture surfaces of neat resins suggested that both type of resins the failure is related with the interface in between bottom layers and normally printed layers. Any strength contribution in this testing scenario is than related to ability of nanoparticles to interact with crack formation at the region interfaces.

Figure 4. Fracture Surfaces of Neat Resins, a-c) AC Neat, b-d) ACT Neat

Figure 5. Flexural Strength of Nanocomposites With Bottom Layer

3.3 EFFECT OF NANOPARTICLES FOR PRINTING WITH THIN BOTTOM LAYERS

The absence of bottom layers enabled the direct contribution of nanoparticles to resin mechanical performance. A significant contribution to flexural strength of ACT was achieved with the use of 5wt% SiO₂ nanoparticles (up to 21 %). When combined with results obtained for thicker bottom layer case, it can be suggested that SLA printing with ACT resins in the presence of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ up to 5 wt. % particle loadings is favorable. In the case of AC resin, only minor strength improvement was achieved by the use of 1 wt. % Al₂O₃. A reduction of strength is observed when stiffer SiC and B₄C nanoparticles are used.

Figure 6. Flexural Strength of Nanocomposites Without Bottom Layer

4 CONCLUSIONS

UV curable resins adapted to additive manufacturing by SLA printing are mixed with four types of different nano-particle types such as Al_2O_3 , B_4C , SiO_2 , SiC . Two types of resins with high rigidity and high toughness were considered. With suggested methodology a large experimentation with 32 different test cases was performed in a quick and reliable manner. When compared with conventional nano-composites research performed on thermosetting materials, the speed advantage of SLA technique is underlined. In total 28 specimen cases were successfully manufactured. Effect of nanoparticles on bottom layer/normal layer interface has been exemplified. Mechanical test results suggested that the presence of bottom layer changes the local mechanical response of printed parts. Strength contribution of each type of particle to tough line (ACT) resin suggested that strength and color tuning was possible with all of the investigated nanoparticles. In the case of rigid line resins, the fracture was more susceptible to nanoparticle present especially on bottom layer/normal layer interfaces. Hence only Al_2O_3 particles appeared adaptable to rigid resins.

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